

DYNAMIC AND TRANSIENT CHARACTERIZATION OF SILICON CARBIDE FIBERS AT ELEVATED TEMPERATURES

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SUMMARY: Ceramic fibers at elevated temperatures exhibit time or frequency dependent mechanical behavior, the most studied of which is creep. Several techniques for characterizing time dependent mechanical properties have been developed in this laboratory. Fibers studied to date include single crystal alumina, YAG, and seven compositions of SiC. Dynamic mechanical spectroscopy methods are used to examine short relaxation time processes associated with periodic deformation phenomena, and provide both dynamic modulus and loss factor versus temperature (to 1600°C) and frequency (from 0.1 to 25 Hz). Pulsed periodic creep and recovery tests are used to examine the longer relaxation time phenomena, and provide an accelerated means to identify and separate anelastic and inelastic creep rates. Taken together these methods provide a comprehensive understanding of the multiplicity of mechanisms and time scales that are relevant to the proper application and design of ceramic fiber reinforced composites.

KEYWORDS: silicon carbide, dynamic testing, creep of ceramics, viscoelasticity, fibers

INTRODUCTION

The analysis of the potential performance of high temperature composite materials and the design of components made from such materials requires detailed information about the constituents of the composite. It is well known that ceramic fibers exhibit high temperature behavior which is time-dependent, i.e., not entirely elastic. In order to gain a more complete understanding of the behavior of ceramic fibers at elevated temperatures and to provide a database for the engineering analysis of composites using these fibers as a reinforcement phase, this laboratory has investigated single fiber behavior using a variety of techniques. In this paper, dynamic mechanical testing and a periodic creep and recovery technique [1] are utilized for the investigation of the viscoelastic properties of ceramic fibers.

BACKGROUND

Materials scientists and engineers commonly use creep testing as a primary means to characterize long term high temperature behavior under applied loads. Generally, creep strain can include elastic, anelastic (viscoelastic) and inelastic (plastic) strain components. Refer to Fig. 1 for a schematic of a creep and recovery test. The elastic contribution to a given creep strain is readily measured by simply removing the sample load and observing the incremental

strain change. Decomposition of the remaining strain into anelastic and inelastic strains can be a challenging task, however. In general, given only a creep curve (strain vs. time) it is not possible to determine what fraction of the strain is anelastic and what fraction inelastic. This determination can be done only by performing a recovery test in which the (recovering) strain vs. time is observed following the removal of the load. The difficulty lies in the fact that as a rule, creep recovery is much slower than creep itself. Presumably, this is because creep recovery occurs with no externally applied load, and given any sort of activated rate theory for the processes involved, the reverse (recovery) process would be expected to involve a higher activation barrier than for the (forward) creep process itself. As a general rule, full recovery of anelastic strains can take as much as ten times longer than the creep itself. Thus a one month creep test might take ten months to fully recover if the strains were entirely anelastic. Clearly, the decomposition of a creep curve into anelastic and inelastic components would involve a series of creep tests for various times, each of which is followed by a longer recovery process. In this way, a long term creep curve could be decomposed into its component anelastic and inelastic strains. From both a mechanistic and design viewpoint, this decomposition is essential. As a corollary, it follows that the measurement of plastic strain rates from a single creep curve is potentially misleading since there would be no basis by which to judge the anelastic (time dependent but recoverable) strains. It is emphasized that the shape of the creep curve (e.g., constant rate) is a very misleading and poor delineator of whether the strain is inelastic or anelastic (or both), as discussed below.

Fig. 1: Loading history and strain response for a typical creep and recovery test.

Guidance regarding the shape of a creep curve which is anelastic can be obtained directly from the theory of linear viscoelasticity (which is not to say that all anelastic processes are linear processes). Anelasticity can be represented by a series of recoverable strains each with a characteristic retardation time, or differently stated, an anelastic process can be represented by its corresponding distribution (or spectrum) of retardation times. For each retardation time, 63% of the anelastic strain component is obtained after a load application for a time equal to one retardation time. It becomes obvious then, that the shape of an anelastic creep curve is dependent on the distribution of retardation times characterizing the creep process. Without additional information, it becomes clear why the shape of the creep curve is a very poor determination of whether the creep is anelastic or inelastic. It follows that a recovery curve of 100 seconds, for example, may fully recover anelastic strains with 10 second or less retardation times, but would not recover any appreciable amount of anelastic strains having

retardation times of longer than 1000 seconds. It is for this reason that we noted earlier that the decomposition of a creep curve into its anelastic and inelastic components requires a series of recovery tests, conducted for several creep times, and not a single recovery test.

Mathematically related to the distribution of retardation times is another distribution referred to as the distribution of relaxation times, which is useful in describing anelastic processes such as stress relaxation or dynamic modulus. Initially, this laboratory engaged in dynamic mechanical testing studies on single ceramic fibers at elevated temperatures, as described elsewhere [4]. In that method a fiber is subjected to a sinusoidally varying displacement and the resulting load measured (without averaging or filtering). The load and displacement signals are then fast Fourier transformed (FFT) to obtain the component of force in-phase and out-of-phase with the displacement, ultimately providing the real (in-phase or storage or elastic) modulus and the imaginary (out-of-phase or loss or viscous) modulus, from which the loss factor can be calculated.

While the real and imaginary components of modulus provide equivalent information on the anelastic processes as does a creep/creep recovery test, they do so at a far different time scale. Dynamic measurements typically emphasize short time scale processes (e.g., relaxation times of milliseconds or less) while creep/recovery tests provide information on long time scale processes (typically retardation times of seconds to years). Thus, the two methods of measurement are complementary and provide a broad picture of material anelastic behavior over many decades of time scale. However, the dynamic modulus measurement method, being intrinsically periodic with a short time scale, quickly reaches steady state, whereas the creep/recovery method being transient, and specifically not periodic, never indicates steady state behavior. A perspective now emerges on the difficulties involved in anelastic/inelastic decomposition of creep and recovery data. The problem of reconstruction of a creep curve into its underlying component anelastic vs. time and inelastic vs. time creep curves is the basis of the test method described here.

There is evidence in the literature that ceramic fibers do exhibit surprising amounts of anelastic behavior. An important observation is given by DiCarlo [2] who performed a creep test on a silicon carbide fiber (SCS-6), followed prudently by an accelerated recovery test at a higher temperature. The creep test was done at 1275°C and 612 MPa, and followed by recovery at 1450°C. Nearly complete recovery was obtained which suggests that the creep curve was primarily anelastic. Additional creep and recovery tests for short time periods have been reported by Lara-Curzio [3]. Dynamic testing of silicon carbide fibers was conducted by Sternstein, Weaver and Beale [4] who found that both the storage and loss modulus varied with the relative amounts of carbon and silicon in the SiC sheath.

PULSED PERIODIC CREEP AND RECOVERY TESTING

One of the useful features of the dynamic test method is its periodic nature, which enables one to quickly establish steady state behavior. The test method utilized here combines the attributes of a periodic test while still offering the benefits of transient (creep) testing which emphasizes long time processes. Referring to Fig. 2, consider a test protocol in which a load is periodically applied to a sample for a period of time t_1 and then removed for some period of time $(t_p - t_1)$ and then the entire cycle repeated every t_p seconds, where t_p is the "period." Further, let the strain at the end of each loading cycle be measured, as well as the strain at the end of each recovery cycle, as shown by the arrows in Fig. 2.

This test is implemented using the apparatus described elsewhere [4] for dynamic modulus testing, but modified with a stiff closed-loop control system and computer which generates the periodic program shown in Fig. 2 and provides for automatic data acquisition. In practice, the load application or removal is done in less than 2 milliseconds without overshoot or ringing, and is made possible by a very stiff and well tuned servo. Data acquisition is done using 18 bit D/A conversion which is required for the high accuracy needed to implement the periodic pulse test. Precision timing for the pulse test history and data acquisition is done in hardware using a 6 MHz crystal, 64 bit pulse counter and interrupt generator. This provides for very precise and reproducible pulse cycles and data acquisition. Cycle periods from 0.5 seconds to days are readily obtained and the number of cycles is limitless, since the data is routinely written to hard disk. The parabolic temperature profile of the fiber testing device requires extraction of the isothermal strain data from the measured displacements by simple calculations described by Feldman and Bahder [5]. A creep activation energy of 580 kJ/mol was found for SiC by true isothermal creep testing of CVD SiC fibers by Lara-Curzio [3], and is supported by DiCarlo [2] for testing under similar conditions as used in the present study.

Fig. 2: Loading history and strain measurement for pulsed periodic creep and recovery testing. Strain measured at $(kt_p)^-$, $k=1\dots N$ and $(kt_p + t_1)^-$, $k=0\dots(N-1)$.

From the theory of linear viscoelasticity, it can be shown that the history described in Fig. 2 produces a slowly accumulating peak strain (the strain measured at the end of each loading cycle) and slowly accumulating recovery strain, with the rate of accumulation being strongly dependent on the ratio of the test time parameters (t_1 , t_p) relative to the retardation times of the material. The mathematics will not be presented here. Suffice it to say that anelastic creep processes having retardation times substantially longer than t_p are effectively "filtered" in that they never get activated (occur) during the loading cycle, while the processes having retardation times shorter or equivalent to t_p are largely recovered after each recovery cycle and therefore do not accumulate as they would if the load were maintained as in a single creep test (without periodic recovery). In effect, the pulsed periodic creep test will always produce less anelastic strain (for a given accumulated time under load, that is t_1 times the number of cycles) than a single creep test of the same time under load. It follows that the resultant "creep curve," that is peak strain vs. accumulated time under load will always be a better representation of the inelastic strain process (if any) than a single creep test. These predictions are fully justified by the experimental results to date, as described below.

Dynamic and pulsed periodic creep testing have been performed on several polycrystalline silicon carbide fibers provided by Textron Specialty Materials. These fibers all have roughly the same morphology (SiC sheath on a carbon core) although they vary slightly in grain size,

composition, and fiber diameter (120 to 150 micrometers). The fibers include the commercially available SCS-6 fiber and a series of five fibers of various composition, herein referred to as EF#1 - EF#5. The composition of the SiC sheath in the SCS fibers is found to vary between stoichiometric and about 1 wt% excess silicon depending on the original chemical vapor deposition (CVD) processing parameters. Additionally, dynamic testing has been performed on British Petroleum's Sigma 1240 fiber. Table 1 lists the atomic carbon / silicon ratio of the fibers used thus far in this study.

Table 1: Composition of various SCS SiC Fibers tested.

Fiber	C / Si atomic ratio
Sigma 1240	0.82
SCS-6	0.96
EF#1	0.99
EF#2	0.99+
EF#3	1.00
EF#4	0.98+
EF#5	0.98

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig. 3 shows the temperature dependence of the storage (Young's) modulus of several of the SiC fibers as determined by dynamic testing. The plot clearly shows the relationship between the amount of excess silicon in the respective fibers (see Table 1) and the retained modulus. The moduli have been normalized by their room temperature values for clarity. Only the Textron experimental fibers #3 and #5 are shown since their behavior brackets the behavior for all of the experimental fibers. Fig. 4 shows a similar behavior for the loss factor with changing composition.

Further underscoring the importance of the C / Si ratio in the SiC sheath of the fiber, pulsed periodic creep testing was conducted under identical conditions for each of the SiC fibers listed in Table 1 (with the exception of BP Sigma 1240). Fig. 5 shows that creep and recovery response of these fibers is clearly dependent upon the stoichiometry of the fiber; the greater the amount of excess silicon present, the higher the creep rate. Further testing is necessary before any statement can be made as to the mechanism by which the excess silicon so drastically controls the high temperature viscoelastic properties of silicon carbide. Again, only the Textron fibers #3 and #5 are shown as their behavior brackets that of the other experimental fibers.

Fig. 3: Normalized Young's modulus at 1 Hz for different CVD silicon carbide fibers. Data is shown for tests conducted with a static stress of 300 MPa (200 MPa for BP Sigma 1240), dynamic stress of 100 MPa.

Fig. 4: High temperature loss behavior of different CVD SiC fibers at 1 Hz. All data is shown for tests performed at 300 MPa static stress, and 100 MPa dynamic stress amplitude.

Fig. 5: Periodic Pulse Testing of SiC fibers of various compositions showing the effect of the C / Si Ratio on the high temperature viscoelastic behavior of SiC. Testing conducted at 1600°C, 200 MPa, and 480 cycles (10 sec. load on, 20 sec. load off).

Fig. 6 shows a comparison between the creep strain developed during a conventional creep test and the peak strain achieved in a pulsed periodic creep test, the latter plotted vs. accumulated time under load. The pulsed data were obtained for a duty cycle consisting of $t_1 = 10$ sec. and $t_p = 30$ sec. Also shown is a single strain point obtained after 9600 seconds of recovery for the single creep test sample. The amount of recovery is large and shows that most of the creep strain which occurred after 4600 seconds was in fact anelastic, not inelastic.

As expected, the pulsed periodic results lie between the single creep results and the recovered strain value. Additional experiments on the effects of various duty cycles (t_1 and t_p values, both as a ratio and absolute values) are currently being performed. While the recovery time to load time for the pulsed periodic test was only 2 to 1 there is still clearly a major reduction in accumulating anelastic strain. While it would be tempting to claim that the slope of the pulsed periodic creep results vs. accumulated loading time is in fact the inelastic (plastic)

strain rate, this would be premature, since other duty cycles with longer recovery to load ratios than 2/1 are required for better suppression of the anelastic strain. Nonetheless, we claim that the slope of the pulsed periodic results is closer to the true inelastic creep rate than the single creep test slope, which is clearly much larger.

Fig. 6: Comparison of Pulse Testing with a Single Creep and Recovery test. Testing of SCS-6 conducted at 200 MPa, 1600°C, 480 cycles (10 sec. load on, 20 sec. load off) versus 4800 sec. creep, 9600 sec. recovery.

The effect of stress magnitude on the pulsed periodic creep test is shown in Fig. 7 for SCS-6 fibers at 1600°C, and it is seen that the creep process is nonlinear, as is also concluded from single cycle creep test data. Finally, the effect of cycle time at constant duty cycle ratio (2/1) is shown in Fig. 8, where it is seen that the results for 15 and 30 second periods are virtually indistinguishable.

CONCLUSIONS

In order to more fully characterize the viscoelastic behavior of silicon carbide at high temperatures it is necessary to employ multiple test methods that target specific relaxation / retardation time scales. Dynamic mechanical testing has been used to investigate the storage and loss modulus (and thus the loss factor) of several silicon carbide fibers whereby the test method only activates relaxation mechanisms with time scales in the millisecond range. Results are presented showing the effect of the carbon / silicon ratio in the SiC sheath on both the retained high temperature modulus and the loss factor.

It appears that the pulsed periodic creep test provides a method whereby the inelastic strain rate may be measured with higher accuracy and more quickly than with single cycle creep tests. Anelastic creep in ceramic fibers at elevated temperatures is surprisingly large in magnitude and covers wide time scales, and therefore significantly affects the slope of a single cycle creep curve, rendering the measurement of inelastic strain rates difficult if not impossible from such a test. The technique used in this study may provide an accelerated and more time efficient method for determining inelastic creep rates. Results are presented

showing the non-linear creep and recovery behavior displayed by SCS-6 silicon carbide fibers. Additional results show the effect of the carbon / silicon ratio in the SiC sheath on the creep and recovery behavior of several CVD fibers of varying composition.

Fig. 7: Comparison of SCS-6 Pulse Testing at 200 MPa and 300 MPa stress showing non-linearity of creep behavior. Tests conducted at 1600°C for 480 cycles (10 sec. load on, 20 sec. load off).

Fig. 8: Comparison of various cycle times (5 sec. load on, 10 sec. load off versus 10 sec. load on, 20 sec. load off) with 1:2 load-on : load-off time ratios. Testing of SCS-6 at 1600°C, 200 MPa, 960 cycles versus 480 cycles.

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REFERENCES

1. Y. H. Park, J. W. Holmes, *J. Mat. Sci.*, 27 (1992) 6341
2. J. A. DiCarlo, *J. Mat. Sci.*, 21 (1986) 217.
3. E. Lara-Curzio, Thermomechanical Characterization of Silicon Carbide Fibers at Elevated Temperatures, PhD. Thesis, Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute, 1992
4. S. S. Sternstein, C. D. Weaver and J. Beale, *Materials Science and Engineering A215* (1996) 9-17.
5. L. A. Feldman, T. B. Bahder, *J. Mat. Sci.*, 8 (1989) 307